

CONTRIBUTION OF ISOTOPE HYDROLOGY TO THE KNOWLEDGE OF TRANSBOUNDARY AQUIFER SYSTEMS IN THE PLURINATIONAL STATE OF BOLIVIA

G.P. FLORES AVILES,

Agencia Boliviana de Energía Nuclear, La Paz, Estado Plurinacional de Bolivia.

E-mail address: gflores@aben.gob.bo

L. ORTEGA

International Atomic Energy Agency, Vienna, Austria.

Abstract: Sustainable management of water resources implies a better knowledge of the behavior of groundwater systems. This study aims at conceptualizing the functioning of a transboundary freshwater reservoir, in the Plurinational State of Bolivia, using scientific isotope data correlated with baseline information. The results provided a good understanding of the aquifer functioning in a pilot zone of the Tierra de los LÍpez Basin, proving that isotope hydrology is a suitable investigation tool to contribute to the progress of transboundary water cooperation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Tierra de los LÍpez Basin [1] is an important transboundary freshwater reservoir shared between Bolivia, Chile and Argentina. The limited understanding about the functioning of groundwater systems is one of the main factors that constrains the progress of operational arrangements [2] for water cooperation in this region. This study aims at conceptualizing the functioning of the Tierra de los LÍpez Transboundary Aquifer basin, in the Laguna Colorada pilot zone, based on scientific evidence of stable and unstable isotopes combined with baseline data.

2. METHODS

During the rainy season of 2019 and the dry season of 2021, two scientific field missions were conducted within the Laguna Colorada pilot zone. A total of 90 measurements of stable isotopes of Oxygen-18, Deuterium, Carbon-13 and of 50 of unstable isotopes of Tritium, Radiocarbon and Radon-222 were performed in samples of: a) 9 groundwater wells (4-9m below ground level), b) 19 springs, and c) surface water from 8 rivers and 2 lagoons. Results were correlated with hydrogeological, hydrological, geophysical and topographic scientific baseline data.

3. RESULTS

The results (Fig.1) allowed determining that the aquifer system, in the pilot zone, consists of: i) a porous subdomain composed of sand, gravel and clay, and ii) a fractured subdomain controlled by the presence of structural systems (faults). Groundwater recharge originates in the mountainous chain of the Western Cordillera, at an altitude of 4.750 to 6.000 m a.s.l. And presents a rate of 7 to 8 mm·year⁻¹ in the porous subdomain. About 58 % of the groundwater volume discharging to the Laguna Colorada evaporates (165.950 – 921.945 m³ year⁻¹).

In the South-West of the aquifer system, groundwater presents a mixing of 39 to 76% of glacial meltwater, 21 to 58% of recent meteoric water, and a minimal influence of geothermal fluids. Moreover, in the North-East and North-West, groundwater presents a mixture of 6 to 94% of water from hydrothermal manifestations, and 5 to 91% of rock glaciers meltwater. Groundwater with apparent ages of 4.612 to 21.603 years has been observed in the aquifer system, implying that recharge is associated with the last glacial-interglacial event of the Bolivian Altiplano characterized by the Tauca lacustrine phase [3].

4. CONCLUSIONS

Isotope hydrology proved to be an effective investigation tool to cope with the lack of science-based information for the sustainable management of transboundary water resources within the Tierra de los LÍpez Basin, in the Plurinational State of Bolivia.

Figure 1. a) Location of the path profile for the 2D cut, and b) 2D aquifer functioning conceptual model of the Tierra de los Lípez Transboundary Basin [4].

REFERENCES

- [1] MINISTERIO DE RELACIONES EXTERIORES DEL ESTADO PLURINACIONAL DE BOLIVIA, Presentación ABEN-MRE (2022) 18 pp.
- [2] U.N.E.C.E., U.N.E.S.C.O., Indicator|SDG 6 Data, <https://sdg6data.org/indicator/6.5.2>. (2022).
- [3] FLORES AVILES, G.P., SPADINI, L., SACCHI, E., ET AL., Hydrogeochemical and nitrate isotopic evolution of a semiarid mountainous basin aquifer of glacial-fluvial and paleolacustrine origin (Lake Titicaca, Bolivia): the effects of natural processes and anthropogenic activities. *Hydrogeol J* 30, (2022) 181–201.
- [4] AGENCIA BOLIVIANA DE ENERGÍA NUCLEAR DEL ESTADO PLURINACIONAL DE BOLIVIA, Aplicación de la Hidrología Isotópica en la Gestión de las Aguas Transfronterizas. CONCLUSIÓN PROYECTO PILOTO EN LA CUENCA TRANSFRONTERIZA TIERRA DE LOS LÍPEZ: Proyecto de Cooperación Técnica BOL 7005 del Estado Plurinacional de Bolivia. N° de Depósito Legal: 4-1-637-2022 P.O.